

Application of Criminal Intelligence Analysis to Apprehend Violent Criminals

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Introduction

Information regarding the crime is the most essential part of the crime that can make people makes an effort to stop the crime. This is why country's police and intelligence agencies focus on obtaining information regarding the crime to adopt precautionary measures for avoiding any kind of unprecedented violent activity. Through analysis of the crime and crime mapping, intelligence agencies are able to track down any kind of violent crime analysis is carried out as one of the mission for utilizing systematic methods to obtain information regarding the crime. Intelligence agencies have recently come up with new ways to employ criminal intelligence to stop violent criminals. This discussion is based on these applications of criminal intelligence analysis to apprehend violent criminals.

Discussion

For intelligence agencies, criminal information is like commodities similar to grain, metals and automobiles. Before any kind of machinery or scientific tactic, information acquired by human beings is one of the most essential initial medium to counter violent criminal acts. Intelligence agencies analyze that whether the piece of information they have obtained is built or mined. There are various sources of data; however, after effective analysis of the data, it becomes information. Later, this information is transformed into knowledge when it is being communicated effectively. Intelligence agencies analyze crimes by taking into account the information, which is communicated and becomes knowledge (Gwinn, Bruce, Cooper & Hick, 2008).

Crime analysis helps in finding hotspots for extra police patrolling. However, this was what was done in the past by the intelligence department. In the contemporary era of crime analysis and intelligence, different products and techniques are being used by the modern police force to indicate any danger of violent or criminal act being done or planned. Intelligence categorizes offensive acts from criminal acts and thus, they also categorize offenders and criminals. In the twentieth century, America modified and improvised the applications of apprehending criminal activities. Police radios and fingerprinting are two major intelligence tactics used by the American police in the twentieth century (Gwinn, Bruce, Cooper & Hick, 2008).

Radios help police force to determine the location of the crime. When criminal activity is planned, police use police radio to track any place with usual kinds of activities and stop the expected violent consequences. There are regular audits and statistical reports produced to check out the rate of crime done in the country every year. This makes intelligence officials have a grip on criminal activities and their types. This makes them plan their actions according to the crimes done and expected. These reports are innovated with new literature, ideas, support, professional standards and trainings (Gwinn, Bruce, Cooper & Hick, 2008).

In United States of America, intelligence agencies are more focused on obtaining information regarding the terrorist and terrorism war activities rather than local crimes. In order to do so, U.S intelligence have improvised all the techniques and methods used in the local crime analysis for the violent crimes done by terrorists. However, this has raised a lot of problems due to the decrease in amounts of funds generated to local police. Professionals in this field have been going through effective training and education so that they are able to meet the criterion for fighting terrorists and their violent criminal planning (Gwinn, Bruce, Cooper & Hick, 2008).

Commitments of intelligence officials are one of the unique characteristics of apprehending violent crimes through effective intelligence procedures. Chief executives of all the intelligence agencies should be viable and sustainable. There should always be an integral survival of command in order to carry out effective anti-violent strategies. It is important for the chief to be independent and confident to take bold decisions regarding national security issues. Secondly, problems of violent crimes should be studied with clarity. No course of action can be planned until and unless there is clarity in the problem, its probable consequences and expected solutions (BJA, 2008).

For example, intelligence agencies dealing with gang crimes obtain every single detail about each and every member of the criminal gang. In this way, collective nature of their crime can be studied and they can be dealt in a much more appropriate manner. This clarity of crime problem and action then leads to clearer picture of statistical data and sheets. Mostly, every country has more than one intelligence agencies working on the similar issues. However, things can be chaotic and confusing if these agencies do not collaborate with one another. The entire network that consists of all the agencies should be based on cooperation and collaboration, in terms of information, strategies, surveillance and actions (BJA, 2008).

Geographic Information System or GIS is one of the software tools that help in analyzing the crime through crime mapping in various ways. This kind of map is a three-dimensional visualization of temporal and spatial data. This tool can be understood through the mechanism of a spreadsheet or a processing program, where data can be collected through templates and frameworks. Thus, crime mapping can be defined as a kind of spatial analysis. In order to adopt crime analysis mapping strategies, American government has introduced favoring policies

(Santos, 2013). Enforcement and policymakers take decisions that favor these types of security and surveillance strategies and tactics (Ratcliffe, 2007).

Developing countries also plan state level policies to eradicate corruption from the society because corruption is also one of the leading causes of the prevalence of violent activities on state and international levels. Government of United States have implemented the policies of free justice, governance, democratic-institution building, political leaders, transparency, rule of law and free press to give Americans every human right and eradicate corruption through any kind of unfair act. Governments have also given the right to different business enterprises that they plan their strategies for marketing and overcoming economic crisis if there is a challenge to national security (Anonymous, 2011).

Conclusion

In conclusion, criminal intelligence and its applications are very integral to the safeguard of national security and homeland. Criminal intelligence is built with an aim that where there is peace, there will always be an emergence of war. American war against terrorism is one of the examples of chaos in the homeland of peace. In order to tackle these criminal activities, nations have to strengthen their intelligence and especially criminal intelligence departments. Governments and armies should always stay welcoming towards the technological advancements done in the field of surveillance and strategies to fight crime. Hence, people should also become active participants in fighting every kind of illegal activity in the society because eradication of violent crimes is a responsibility for everyone.

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